

THE DEVELOPMENT OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USED IN THE PRODUCTION OF REFERENCE MATERIALS

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper presents the development of Quality Management System (QMS) used in the production of Reference Materials (RM), specific to food engineering.

Methodology/approach - The authors performed a documentary study on the legislation applied in the accreditation of manufacturers of RM. In order to develop the QMS, the procedures specific to the certified RM field were identified.

Findings – This paper presents the specific procedures for the development of the QMS necessary for the accreditation of the manufacturers of reference materials according to the clauses of the ISO 17034 standard.

Research limitations/implications – This research paper presents the requirements of ISO standards in the area of production of reference materials and synthesis of management procedures in the field of quality development of reference materials in the sector of food engineering.

Practical implications – The documentary study allowed the National Institute of Research and Development for Food Bioresources – IBA Bucharest, to elaborate the documentation needed to create the QMS for the development of RM.

Originality/value – The paper shows that in addition to the necessary infrastructure, for the development of the quality system in the production of RM, at least 30 specific procedures and 20 work instructions are required, and over 40 standard forms.

Key words: quality management system; production of reference material; ISO 17034:2017 standard

1. Introduction

Major incidents of food frauds reported at European Union member states level led to the elaboration in 2013 of the European Parliament Resolution, which called the European Commission to pay all the needed attention to food fraud and to take all necessary measures such as the prevention and battle against food fraud in order to become an integrated part of the EU policy (Committee on the Environment, 2013).

At the same time, given the scale of food fraud, its consequences on human health and the economic climate, the European Commission has set up a Center for Food Fraud and Quality, starting March 13, 2018, operating within the Joint Research Center (JRC). The newly created entity supports innovation in the field of testing techniques, by developing/standardizing new methods and increasing the measurement performance.

The quality of measurements plays a key role in technological and socio-economic development, thus supporting the development of trade and monitoring the quality of products and services and allows the optimization of decisions in monitoring food safety (Rychlik et al., 2018).

The quality of the test results is monitored both internally and externally by using certified reference materials (MRC). Consequently, the development of MRC is a vital area in the quality control of the test result and implicitly of food safety.

The reference material (RM) is the generic name used to refer to that material that is sufficiently homogeneous and stable related to one or more of the specified characteristics and determined to be suitable for the intended use in a measurement process. The specified characteristics can be quantitative or qualitative, and the uses could include calibration of the measurement system, evaluation of the measurement procedure, allocation of values of other materials and quality control. The nutritional value of the products is of particular importance for the labeling of foods for the international trade in goods and the support schemes of the common agricultural policy.

William Cunningham defines in Chapter 3, related to RMs, from the book of reference material producers, published under the U.S. Food and Drug Administration, three types of reference materials namely: RM, certified reference materials (CRM) and reference materials produced by an internal laboratory (IRM) (C. & G., 2014).

If during the '80s the requirements regarding the competence of the reference material producers were not standardized, with the intensification of the quality of test monitoring, the ISO Guide 34:2009 was elaborated, which laid-down "General requirements for the competence of the producers of RMs"(International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2009).

In 2016, the International Organization for Standardization published the ISO 17034:2016 standard on general requirements regarding the competence of reference material producers (RMP), replacing ISO Guide 34:2009. The need for an international standard arose because several accreditation bodies could not accredit against the guide, while in other countries ISO Guide 34 was accepted in accreditation only in combination with ISO 17025, the RMP being obliged to accredit also in compliance with the requirements of ISO 17025 (International Standard Organization, 2005).

In addition, at European level, the legislation establishes the requirements for accreditation and market surveillance and Regulation (EC) no. 765/2008 (European Parliament, 2008) requires that the accreditation should be based on harmonized international standards. Therefore, accreditation according to a guide is only accepted for a transitional period and is not possible in the long term, therefore, ISO Guide 34:2009 is no longer applicable.

The testing laboratories use RMs for calibrating the measuring instruments, validating the methods, evaluating the test procedures and for controlling the quality of the results.

2. Materials and Methods

This paper presents the specific procedures for the development of the quality management system necessary for the accreditation of the manufacturers of reference materials according to the clauses of the ISO 17034 standard.

In this sense, the authors performed a documentary study on the legislation applied in the accreditation of manufacturers of reference materials. Also, in order to develop the quality system management, the procedures specific to the MRC field were identified.

ISO 17034 standard contains requirements for Reference Material Producers (PRMs) required for accreditation (International Organization for Standardization, 2016). PRMs that meet the requirements of ISO 17034 are considered competent. At the same time, reference materials that meet the requirements of this Standard must be accompanied by a certificate with mentions about the homogeneity and stability of the specified properties. Also, the certified reference material (CRMs) are accompanied with the certified value, the associated measurement uncertainty and metrological traceability.

The European Union has been supporting the development/production of RMs for more than four decades, with the establishment of the European Community Reference Office (BCR) in 1980. For

example, BCR produces wheat flour certified as RM (BCR-563 and BCR-396) for the parameters presented in Table 1 (Steger, 1983) (European Commission, 2016) (European Commission, 2019).

Table 1. Certified quality parameters for BCR-563 wheat flour

No.	Name	Parameter/technique
1	Physical properties	- weight per hectoliter/ water content, ash content
2	Presence of proteins	- protein and / or gluten content/ protein composition and amino acids
3	Rheological properties	- test farinograph or valorigraph/ value alveograph/ -test extensograph
4	Enzyme properties	- Hagberg drop number/ amilograph
5	Other examinations	- Mycotoxin content/ pesticide and insecticide residues

Table 2. ISO standards applicable in the production or use of reference materials

Standard	Standard title
ISO/CEI 17025	General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories
ISO 17034	General requirements for the competence of the reference material manufacturers
ISO Guide 30	Terms and definitions used in the reference standards (www.iso.org)
Guide ISO 31	Reference materials. Content of certificates of reference materials
ISO Guide 32	Calibration of chemical analyzes / use of reference materials certificates
ISO Guide 33	Good practice in using reference materials
ISO Guide 35	Guidance for characterization and assessment of homogeneity and stability
ISO 17034	General requirements for the competence of the reference material manufacturers
ISO Guide 80	Guidance for the in-house preparation of quality control materials (QCMs)
ISO/TR 79	Reference materials - Examples of reference materials for qualitative properties
ISO/TR 10989	Reference materials - Guidance on, and keywords used for, RM categorization
NIST 260-100	User's Manual for Reference Materials

The documentation for accreditation of reference material producers based on SR EN ISO 17034:2017 standard. The SR EN ISO 17034:2017 documents are presented in table 3.

Table 3. The SR ISO CEN 17034:2016 documents for accreditation system of reference material producers

No.	Name	Description	Number
1	ISO 17034 Quality Manual	-the requirements for accreditation of reference material producers	1
2	Procedures	-all the specific practice areas	29
3	Work instructions	-establishing a good quality control environment	20
4	Forms	-standard forms	40
5	Audit	-audit questions for internal auditing system SR EN ISO 17034	200

3. Results and discussions

In Romania, the National Institute of Research and Development for Food Bioresources – IBA Bucharest (Romania) benefits from national funding for increasing the expertise in production of RMs, specific to food engineering, in accordance with the European Commission recommendations. Thus, National Plan for Research, Development and Innovation 2015-2020 funded the projects PN 19 02 04 01 "Research on the development of skills in the development of reference materials and inter laboratory comparisons". The documents elaborated for the implementation of the quality management in the laboratory for the production of reference materials are presented in table 4.

Table 4. Document matrix SR EN ISO 17034:2017 (QM=Quality Manual; P=Procedure; F=Form)

No.	Reference ISO 17034	Abbreviation	Title
1	4	P	Procedure for Request, tender and contract reviews
2	4.2	P	Procedure for impartiality or operational integrity
3	4.3	P	Procedure for protection of customer's confidential information
4	6.1	P	Procedure for personnel and training
5	6.1	F	Training Calendar/ Training report/ Job Description
6	6.2	P	Procedure for subcontracting
7	6.3	P	Procedure for procurement of equipment and services
8	6.3	F	Registration/ Inspection report
9	6.4	P	Procedure for accommodation and environment
10	6.4	F	Environment condition monitoring report
11	7.2	P	Procedure for production planning and implementation
12	7.2	F	Production plan
13	7.3	P	Procedure for production control
14	7.4	P	Procedure for labeling and packaging
15	7.4	F	Packing report/ Deliver challan
16	7.5	P	Procedure for material processing
17	7.6	P	Procedure for Measurement procedures
18	7.7	P	Procedure for equipment
19	7.7	F	Preventive Maintenance
20	7.8	P	Procedure for protecting the integrity of data
21	7.9	P	Procedure for metrological traceability
22	7.1	P	Procedure for assessment of homogeneity
23	7.11	P	Procedure for assessment of stability
24	7.11	F	Stability study report
25	7.12	P	Procedures for characterization
26	7.13	P	Procedure for assignment of property values
27	7.13	F	Uncertainty calculation report
28	7.14	QM	Description of documents and labels
29	7.15	QM	Method followed for distribution
30	7.16	P	Procedure for control of records
31	7.17	P	Procedure for Control of non-conforming reference materials
32	7.17	F	Non-conforming work report
33	7.18	P	Procedure for complaint handling
34	8.2	F	Quality objective monitoring report
35	8.3	QM	Structure of management system documetation
36	8.4	P	Procedure for control on management system documents
37	8.4	F	Distribution list of documents
38	8.5	P	Procedure for control of records
39	8.6	P	Procedure for management review
40	8.7	P	Procedure for internal audit
41	8.7	F	Audit plan/ Internal audit non-conformity report/ Audit programme
42	8.8	QM	Risk and opportunities
43	8.9	P	Procedure for corrective action
44	8.9	F	Corrective action report
45	8.1	QM	Methods followed for improvements
46	8.11	F	Customer feedback report

In 2018, the SR ISO 17025 standard was revised and, thus, the possibility of its integration in the quality system certified according to the SR ISO 9001 standard was introduced.

In direction with the new trend in the field of quality testing of agri-food products, the integrated standards are presented in Figure 1 as follows: the standards EN ISO 17034 "General requirements for competence of manufacturers of reference materials" and ISO 17043 "General requirements for tests of competence", suppliers of conformities in the EN ISO / IEC 17025 standard are implemented in an ISO 9001 certified quality system.

Figura 1. Scheme of integrated quality system used in the manufacturing of Reference Materials and organizing of interlaboratory comparison schemes

Underlying the need to develop the international standard was the impossibility of independent accreditation of the ISO 34: 2009 Guide, without forcing the manufacturer of reference materials to be accredited according to ISO 17025. The transformation allowed alignment with recent editions of conformity assessment standards in the series ISO 17000, mainly: ISO 17025 (general laboratory quality) and ISO 17043 (proficiency testing). This is considered an advantage for manufacturers of reference materials who perform analytical measurements and organize proficiency tests.

Conclusions

Regarding the quality of RM, the ISO 17034 standard establishes requirements for assessing their homogeneity and stability because they have a major influence on defining RM characteristics. Thus, the homogeneity test is required for all the characterization schemes of the RM, because it provides information on possible variations of inhomogeneity, the presence of impurities or deficiencies in the production of granular reference materials.

In addition to the necessary infrastructure, for the development of the quality system in the production of reference materials, at least 30 specific procedures and 20 work instructions are required, and over 40 standard forms.

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